

Distributed Reconstruction of Sensor Cyber-Attacks in Cyber-Physical Networks

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Abstract—Critical infrastructures, such as power and transportation, are frequently modeled as interconnected Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS). This interconnectivity makes CPS vulnerable to cyber-attacks, threatening system stability and operational continuity. Notably, many of these malicious attacks involve manipulating sensor measurements. In this context, accurately reconstructing the attack signal is crucial for recovering true measurements, distinguishing cyber-attacks from faults, and enabling effective countermeasures. This work presents a distributed scheme that leverages sliding mode observers to reconstruct attack signals targeting sensors in heterogeneous linear cyber-physical networks. The proposed approach achieves attack reconstruction with suitable bounds on the reconstruction error that depend on the system disturbance characteristics. Additionally, we present an isolation mechanism that utilizes the developed reconstruction scheme and analytically show that it accurately determines the attacked nodes. The applicability of the proposed approach is demonstrated through numerical simulations on a six-subsystem interconnected system, which validate our analytic results.

I. INTRODUCTION

Motivation: Large-scale Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) integrate computational and physical processes, enhancing critical infrastructure sectors like energy, transportation, and healthcare [1]. Their extensive geographical distribution often necessitates distributed control approaches for complexity management and effective coordination [2]. As CPS integration increases, the demand for robust security intensifies, particularly against sophisticated cyber-attacks that threaten information integrity, availability, and confidentiality [3]. Control system methodologies offer an effective framework for detecting and isolating these attacks by leveraging dynamic models for real-time monitoring and rapid anomaly response [4]–[6]. A key aspect of this safeguarding process is the accurate reconstruction of sensor attack signals. This reconstruction allows recovery of true measurements impacted by attacks, ensuring operational continuity despite cybersecurity threats [7]. Developing distributed approaches is crucial for large-scale CPS, enabling scalability and mitigating single points of failure [8]. Thus, achieving distributed sensor attack reconstruction in large-scale CPS is highly significant for robust defense against cyber threats, ensuring

the reliability of critical infrastructures in an increasingly digital and interconnected world.

Related Works: Cyber-attack detection and isolation are crucial for CPS security [3], [9]. Many CPS security approaches derive from established Fault Detection and Isolation (FDI) research [10]. While some FDI techniques apply to CPS security, their unique challenges must be considered [11]. Observer-based schemes, including Kalman filtering [4], sliding mode techniques [5], [12], adaptive control [6], and unknown input observers [13], have shown notable effectiveness among FDI approaches. Sensor-related FDI is well-explored [14], [15]. For instance, [16] proposes a distributed FDI approach using structured residuals and fault signature matrices to isolate sensor faults. [17] differentiates sensor replay attacks from physical faults via watermarking, while [18] uses an isolability metric based on threat basis functions for a similar problem. Additionally, [19] developed a distributed fault diagnosis algorithm combining consensus-based and local Kalman filters in sensor networks. The Sliding Mode Observer (SMO) technique is widely used for fault detection and reconstruction, proving robust against actuator and sensor faults amid system uncertainties [20], [21]. Although SMO use for attack reconstruction is limited, insights from fault diagnosis are applicable. For example, [22] proposed a fault reconstruction method for consensus dynamics, maintaining system integrity despite compromised data. Furthermore, [23] presented a distributed SMO-based method for identifying and reconstructing false data injection attacks in DC microgrids. Current research on distributed attack and fault reconstruction primarily focuses on actuator faults [24], [25], which do not directly affect state measurements, enabling fault diagnosis in multi-agent systems [26], [27]. In contrast, reconstructing sensor faults or attacks poses novel challenges due to their impact on measurement reliability [8]. Few studies address distributed reconstruction of sensor faults and attacks [28]–[32]. These works typically transform the system into a descriptor form to estimate extended states, assuming homogeneous dynamics and attempting to reconstruct the attack by estimating entire network states. Consequently, developing distributed attack reconstruction and isolation for heterogeneous large-scale systems remains a critical literature gap.

Contribution: This paper addresses the distributed reconstruction of sensor attacks in heterogeneous linear systems subject to disturbances. We propose a novel methodology for identifying compromised subsystems and reconstructing attack signals corrupting their sensor measurements. Our approach leverages distributed observer schemes combined with sliding mode techniques, ideal for large-scale CPSs. For attacked sensors, the reconstructed signal captures the malicious input with a known error margin, while for unaf-

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ected sensors, it yields a bounded value close to zero. We analyze conditions for false alarms, offering insights into operational limitations for interconnected CPS monitoring. Moreover, utilizing the developed reconstruction scheme, we introduce a distributed isolation mechanism that identifies compromised subsystems based on local alarm signal analysis and inter-node communication. The effectiveness of our approach is validated via numerical simulations on a six-subsystem interconnected system, demonstrating accurate attack signal reconstruction and reliable isolation of the attacked subsystems, even with disturbances. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that simultaneously addresses the distributed reconstruction and isolation of sensor attack signals in large-scale interconnected CPS with heterogeneous dynamics .

Paper Structure: Section II outlines the system and attack models, defining the problem. In Section III, we present our distributed SMO design. Section IV details our methodology for distributed attack reconstruction, followed by our approach to isolating attacked subsystems in Section V. Section VI provides the paper’s main result, validated through numerical simulations in Section VII. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VIII. [The proof of all results are omitted due to space limitations and will be provided in an extended version of this work.](#)

Preliminaries: The Euclidean norm of a vector or the induced norm of a matrix is denoted by $\|\cdot\|$. The sign function, $\text{sign}(x)$, returns 1 for $x > 0$, -1 for $x < 0$, and 0 for $x = 0$. The function $\mathbb{1}(x)$ returns 1 if $x > 0$ and 0 otherwise. The pseudo-inverse of a matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is denoted by A^\dagger . A matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is positive semidefinite (PSD) if $x^\top A x \geq 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, or equivalently, if all its eigenvalues are non-negative, denoted as $A \succeq 0$. For vectors $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $v \succeq 0$ indicates that all components of v are non-negative. A graph is represented as $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, with \mathcal{V} as the set of nodes and \mathcal{E} as the set of edges. A graph is undirected if $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$ implies $(j, i) \in \mathcal{E}$; otherwise, it is directed . A directed graph is strongly connected if every node is reachable from any other node. The in-neighborhood and out-neighborhood of a node i are $\mathcal{N}_i^{\text{in}} = \{j \in \mathcal{V} \mid (j, i) \in \mathcal{E}\}$ and $\mathcal{N}_i^{\text{out}} = \{j \in \mathcal{V} \mid (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}\}$, respectively.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System Model

We consider a large-scale system of N interconnected linear dynamical subsystems, forming a graph $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ where $\mathcal{V} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ are nodes and $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ are edges representing interactions. Each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$ has dynamics:

$$\dot{x}^i = A^i x^i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{in}}} H^{ij} x^j + B^i u^i + D^i w^i, \quad (1a)$$

$$y^i = C^i x^i + \delta^i, \quad (1b)$$

where $A^i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_i}$, $H^{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_j}$, $B^i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times m_i}$, $C^i \in \mathbb{R}^{p_i \times n_i}$, and $D^i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times d_i}$. x^i is state, u^i control input, y^i sensor measurement, w^i disturbance, and δ^i a sensor attack. $\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{in}}} H^{ij} x^j$ captures neighbor influence. Physically linked nodes exchange information via a cyber layer, allowing distributed control.

For streamlined notation, the dynamics are:

$$\dot{x}^i = A^i x^i + H^i x^{-i} + B^i u^i + D^i w^i,$$

where $H^i = [H^{i,j_1} \dots H^{i,j_{d_i^{\text{in}}}}] \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times m_i}$ (with $m_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{in}}} n_j$) concatenates coupling matrices for $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{in}}$. $x^{-i} = [x^{j_1}, \dots, x^{j_{d_i^{\text{in}}}}]^T$ contains neighboring states. Assumptions for (1):

Assumption 1. For $i \in \mathcal{V}$, the invariant zeros of the pair (A^i, C^i) have negative real parts.

This ensures system stability by guaranteeing poles related to invariant zeros lie in the left half-plane, indicating asymptotic stability.

Assumption 2. The state disturbance w^i is a zero-mean random process. Its magnitudes satisfy:

$$\|w^i\| < \bar{w}^i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \quad (2)$$

where \bar{w}^i is a known constant.

This establishes an upper limit on local disturbance magnitudes, reflecting practical physical/sensor constraints.

B. Attack Model

We address integrity attacks on sensor measurements, where an attacker injects malicious signals. Attackers are assumed to know system dynamics and access communication/sensors. Attacks on sensor i start at T_a^i , with the malicious signal $\delta^i(t)$ defined as:

$$\delta^i(t) = \psi^i(t) \cdot \mathbb{1}(t - T_a^i), \quad (3)$$

where $\psi^i(t)$ is the attack signal and $\mathbb{1}(t - T_a^i)$ is the unit step function at T_a^i . The following assumption is made to ensure that the system remains on the sliding surface during an attack, as will be described in Section III.

Assumption 3. The attack signal magnitude satisfies:

$$\|\delta^i\| \leq \bar{\delta}^i, \quad \|\dot{\delta}^i\| \leq \bar{d}^i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\delta}^i$ and \bar{d}^i are known constants.

The variable $\psi^i(t)$ in (3) models various attack types: *replay attacks* ($\psi^i(t) = -y^i(t) + y^i(t - \tau_i)$), *denial of service (DoS) attacks* ($\psi^i(t) = -y^i(t)$), and *false data injection attacks* ($\psi^i(t) = -y^i(t) + f_i(t)$, with $f_i(t)$ a malicious signal).

C. Problem Statement

This paper addresses the following problem:

Problem 1. For system (1) and attack model (3), let $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ be the set of attacked nodes. Design a distributed scheme to:

- i) Identify and isolate the set of attacked nodes \mathcal{M} .
- ii) Reconstruct the local attack for each node $i \in \mathcal{M}$ with a known error bound.

In essence, the goal is a distributed monitoring scheme to detect attacked subsystems and estimate their attack signals with guaranteed error bounds.

III. DISTRIBUTED SLIDING MODE OBSERVER DESIGN

Under Assumption 1, a coordinate transformation $\tilde{x}^i = T^i x^i = \begin{bmatrix} S^i \\ C^i \end{bmatrix} x^i$ (with invertible T^i) brings the system into canonical form suitable for sliding mode observation [24]. The transformed system dynamics are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\tilde{x}}_1^i \\ \dot{\tilde{y}}_c^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{11}^i & \mathcal{A}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{A}_{21}^i & \mathcal{A}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{x}_1^i \\ \tilde{y}_c^i \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{H}_1^i \\ \mathcal{H}_2^i \end{bmatrix} \tilde{x}^{-i} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{B}_1^i \\ \mathcal{B}_2^i \end{bmatrix} u^i + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{D}_1^i \\ \mathcal{D}_2^i \end{bmatrix} w^i, \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{y}_c^i = \tilde{x}_2^i = C^i x^i$ is the corrected (attack-free) sensor measurement. Calligraphic letters denote transformed matrices.

A distributed state observer for system (5) is designed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{x}}_1^i \\ \dot{\hat{y}}^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{11}^i & \mathcal{A}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{A}_{21}^i & \mathcal{A}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{x}_1^i \\ \hat{y}^i \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{H}_1^i \\ \mathcal{H}_2^i \end{bmatrix} \hat{x}^{-i} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{B}_1^i \\ \mathcal{B}_2^i \end{bmatrix} u^i + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ K^i \end{bmatrix} \nu^i, \quad (6)$$

where $\nu^i = \text{sign}(e_2^i)$ is the switching gain, and $e_2^i = \tilde{y}^i - \hat{y}^i$ is the output estimation error.

We assume that for each subsystem i , the combined set of its in-neighbors and itself contains at most one attacked node:

Assumption 4. For each subsystem $i \in \mathcal{V}$, $|(N_i^{\text{in}} \cup \{i\}) \cap \mathcal{M}| \leq 1$, where \mathcal{M} is the set of attacked subsystems.

Assumption 4 is practical for geographically distributed systems, as simultaneous compromise of multiple nodes is difficult. Future work will explore relaxing this assumption for broader applicability.

The state estimation error $\begin{bmatrix} e_1^i \\ e_2^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{x}_1^i - \hat{x}_1^i \\ \tilde{y}_c^i + \delta^i - \hat{y}^i \end{bmatrix}$ evolves as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_1^i \\ \dot{e}_2^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{11}^i & \mathcal{A}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{A}_{21}^i & \mathcal{A}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_1^i \\ e_2^i \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{A}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \delta^i - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ K^i \end{bmatrix} \nu^i + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{H}_{11}^i & \mathcal{H}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{H}_{21}^i & \mathcal{H}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_1^{-i} \\ e_2^{-i} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{D}_1^i \\ \mathcal{D}_2^i \end{bmatrix} w^i + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \delta^i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

We do *not* assume a slowly-varying attack; hence, δ^i is explicitly retained in the error dynamics. The sliding surface is defined as

$$\sigma(e) = \{e_1^1, \dots, e_2^N : e_2^1 = 0, \dots, e_2^N = 0\}. \quad (8)$$

Once sliding motion is achieved, dynamics (7) become:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_1^i \\ \dot{e}_0^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{11}^i & \mathcal{A}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{A}_{21}^i & \mathcal{A}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_1^i \\ e_0^i \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{A}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \delta^i - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ K^i \end{bmatrix} \nu_{eq}^i + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{H}_{11}^i & \mathcal{H}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{H}_{21}^i & \mathcal{H}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_1^{-i} \\ e_0^{-i} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{D}_1^i \\ \mathcal{D}_2^i \end{bmatrix} w^i + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \delta^i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where ν_{eq}^i is the equivalent output injection term. The following proposition shows that, on the sliding surface, the estimation error e_1^i is bounded.

Proposition 1. Consider (1) and let Assumptions 1–4 hold. Additionally, assume there exist positive definite matrices P_1^i and positive constants α_i such that:

$$(A_{11}^i)^T P_1^i + P_1^i A_{11}^i \preceq -I, \quad (10a)$$

$$\alpha_i > \|P_1^i\|, \quad (10b)$$

$$\mathbf{Q}(\alpha)^T + \mathbf{Q}(\alpha) \succ 0, \quad (10c)$$

$$\mathbf{R}(\alpha) \succeq 0, \quad (10d)$$

where $\alpha = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_N]$, each element q_{ij} of $\mathbf{Q}(\alpha)$ is defined as:

$$q_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i = j, \\ -2\alpha_i \|\mathcal{H}_{11}^{ij}\|, & \text{if } j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{in}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and $\mathbf{R}(\alpha)$ is a row vector where each element r_i is given by $r_i = 2\alpha_i (\|\mathcal{A}_{12}^i\| \bar{\delta}^i + \|\mathcal{D}_1^i\| \bar{w}^i)$. Then, if $e \in \sigma(e)$, then $[e_1^1, \dots, e_1^N] \in X$, where the compact set X is given by:

$$X = \{e_1^1, \dots, e_1^N : [\|e_1^1\| \dots \|e_1^m\|] \preceq 2\mathbf{R}(\alpha)(\mathbf{Q}^T(\alpha) + \mathbf{Q}(\alpha))^{-1}\}.$$

While Proposition 1 ensures e_1^i is bounded on the sliding surface (8), designing a gain to reach this surface requires a pre-sliding bound [33]. Thus, we assume:

Assumption 5. There exist known constants $\rho^i > 0$ such that

$$\|e_1^i\| \leq \rho^i, \quad (11)$$

for $i \in \mathcal{V}$, where e_1^i is defined in (7).

The following result demonstrates that a suitable gain K^i drives the system to the sliding surface and maintains it.

Proposition 2. Let Assumptions 1–5 hold. Then, system (7) will be driven to the sliding surface (8) in finite time, and the sliding motion will be maintained if

$$K^i > \|\mathcal{A}_{21}^i\| \rho^i + \|\mathcal{A}_{22}^i\| \bar{\delta}^i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{in}}} \|\mathcal{H}_{21}^{ij}\| \rho^j + \|\mathcal{D}_2^i\| \bar{w}^i + \bar{d}^i, \quad (12)$$

for each subsystem $i \in \mathcal{V}$.

IV. DISTRIBUTED SENSOR ATTACK SIGNAL RECONSTRUCTION

Throughout the remainder of this work, we assume the sliding surface (8) has been reached. When sliding motion is achieved, the error dynamics are described by (9), which can be compactly written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_1^i \\ \dot{e}_0^i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{11}^i & \mathcal{H}_{11}^i & \mathcal{A}_{12}^i & \mathcal{H}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{A}_{21}^i & \mathcal{H}_{21}^i & \mathcal{A}_{22}^i & \mathcal{H}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_1^i \\ e_0^i \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{12}^i \\ \mathcal{A}_{22}^i \end{bmatrix} \delta^i - \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ K^i \end{bmatrix} \nu_{eq}^i + \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{D}_1^i \\ \mathcal{D}_2^i \end{bmatrix} w^i + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \delta^i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

Due to subsystem stability, \dot{e}_1^i approaches zero. From the first row of (13), at steady state we have $[e_1^i \ e_0^{-i}]^T = ([\mathcal{A}_{11}^i \ \mathcal{H}_{11}^i])^\dagger (\mathcal{A}_{12}^i \delta^i - \mathcal{D}_1^i w^i)$. Substituting this into the second row of the error dynamics yields $M_\delta^i \delta^i - K^i \nu_{eq}^i - M_v^i w^i + \delta^i = 0$, where

$$M_\delta^i = [\mathcal{A}_{21}^i \ \mathcal{H}_{21}^i] ([\mathcal{A}_{11}^i \ \mathcal{H}_{11}^i])^\dagger \mathcal{A}_{12}^i - \mathcal{A}_{22}^i, \quad (14a)$$

$$M_v^i = [\mathcal{A}_{21}^i \ \mathcal{H}_{21}^i] ([\mathcal{A}_{11}^i \ \mathcal{H}_{11}^i])^\dagger \mathcal{D}_1^i - \mathcal{D}_2^i. \quad (14b)$$

Rearranging these terms, we obtain $\delta^i = (M_\delta^i)^\dagger (K^i \nu_{eq}^i + M_v^i w^i - \delta^i)$.

Since w^i and δ^i are unknown, we define the reconstruction signal as:

$$\hat{\delta}^i = (M_\delta^i)^\dagger K^i \nu_{eq}^i, \quad (15)$$

and treat w^i and δ^i as reconstruction disturbances. The attack reconstruction error is then bounded by:

$$\|\delta^i - \hat{\delta}^i\| \leq \|(M_\delta^i)^\dagger M_v^i\| \bar{w}^i + \|(M_\delta^i)^\dagger\| \bar{d}^i, \quad (16)$$

where \bar{d}^i is given in Assumption 5. To detect attacks, each subsystem locally computes $\hat{\delta}^i$ via (15). Before analyzing attack scenarios, we establish a baseline for the reconstruction error in attack-free conditions.

Proposition 3. *Let Assumptions 1–5 hold, and consider the observer (6) for system (1), with SMO gain satisfying (12) for all $i \in \mathcal{V}$. If $\delta^i = 0$ for all $i \in \mathcal{V}$ and $e \in \sigma(e)$ from (8), then the reconstruction signal $\hat{\delta}^i$ computed via (15) satisfies:*

$$\|\hat{\delta}^i\| \leq \|(M_\delta^i)^\dagger M_v^i\| \bar{w}^i \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{V}. \quad (17)$$

Based on Proposition 3, we define a local threshold ϵ^i for each subsystem $i \in \mathcal{V}$:

$$\epsilon^i = \|(M_\delta^i)^\dagger M_v^i\| \bar{w}^i. \quad (18)$$

This threshold represents the maximum expected norm for the reconstruction signal $\hat{\delta}^i$ under attack-free conditions in subsystem i . We then define the alarm signal $a^i(t)$ as:

$$a^i(t) = \begin{cases} \text{True}, & \text{if } \exists t' \leq t \text{ such that } \|\hat{\delta}^i(t')\| > \epsilon^i, \\ \text{False}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

The alarm $a^i(t)$ activates when $\|\hat{\delta}^i\|$ exceeds ϵ^i , indicating a potential attack in subsystem i . Building upon this detection mechanism, the following proposition details how alarms trigger in attacked nodes and propagate through the network.

Proposition 4. *Let Assumptions 1–5 hold. Consider the observer defined by (6) for system (1), where the SMO gain satisfies (12) for all $i \in \mathcal{V}$, and assume $e \in \sigma(e)$ as per (8). If subsystem i is under attack and the magnitude of the attack signal $\|\delta^i\|$ satisfies:*

$$\|\delta^i\| > \max \left\{ 2\epsilon^i, \max_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{out}}} \frac{\epsilon^j}{\|(M_\delta^j)^\dagger M_\delta^{ji}\|} \right\},$$

where ϵ^k is defined in (18), M_δ^j in (14a), and M_δ^{ji} is:

$$M_\delta^{ji} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{21}^j & \mathcal{H}_{21}^j \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{A}_{11}^j & \mathcal{H}_{11}^j \end{bmatrix} \right)^\dagger \mathcal{H}_{12}^{ji} - \mathcal{H}_{22}^{ji}. \quad (20)$$

Then:

- 1) The alarm $a^i(t)$ will be correctly triggered in the attacked node i .
- 2) The alarm $a^j(t)$ will be triggered in all direct out-neighbors $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{out}}$ of the attacked node, even if they are not directly under attack.
- 3) The alarm will not propagate to nodes j that are neither attacked nor direct out-neighbors of the attacked node (i.e., $j \notin \{\mathcal{N}_i^{\text{out}} \cup \{i\}\}$), maintaining $\|\hat{\delta}^j\| < \epsilon^j$.

V. ATTACK ISOLATION

In the previous section, we established that alarms are triggered when the magnitude of an attack surpasses a specified threshold. This section focuses on developing conditions for isolating the attacked subsystem using the designed Sliding Mode Observers. We introduce the following assumption regarding the attack magnitude:

Fig. 1: Information flow for a three-subsystem network.

Assumption 6. *For each attacked subsystem $i \in \mathcal{M}$, there exists some time-instant t such that:*

$$\|\delta^i(t)\| \geq \max \left\{ 2\epsilon^i, \max_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{out}}} \frac{\epsilon^j}{\|(M_\delta^j)^\dagger M_\delta^{ji}\|} \right\}, \quad (21)$$

where ϵ^i is defined in (18) and M_δ^j and M_δ^{ji} are defined in (14a) and (20), respectively.

Assumption 6 guarantees that the attack is sufficiently large, at least at one time instant, to trigger alarms in both the attacked subsystems and all their direct out-neighbors. It's important to note that Assumption 6 does not conflict with Assumption 3; the latter is for observer stability, while the former supports attack isolation. Future research will explore relaxing these assumptions for broader applicability and enhanced robustness.

If Assumption 6 holds, we can conclude that an attack will activate alarms in both the affected subsystems $i \in \mathcal{M}$ and all their out-neighbors. To clearly illustrate this information flow, Figure 1 depicts the proposed scheme within a simplified three-node graph. According to Assumption 4, only one of these subsystems can be under attack at any given time.

Based on these considerations, we define the set of candidate attacked nodes as:

$$\mathcal{V}_a = \{i \in \mathcal{V} : a_k = 1, \forall k \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{out}} \cup \{i\}\}. \quad (22)$$

The set \mathcal{V}_a comprises all nodes for which both the node itself and all its out-neighbors have active alarms. This set is crucial for isolating the actual attacked nodes, as further elaborated below.

To effectively isolate the attack and prevent its propagation through neighboring subsystems, we introduce the following assumption on the attack location:

Assumption 7. *Each node $i \notin \mathcal{M}$ has at least one out-neighbor j that is not an out-neighbor of any attacked node, i.e.,*

$$\forall i \notin \mathcal{M}, \quad \exists j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{\text{out}} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad j \notin \bigcup_{k \in \mathcal{M}} \mathcal{N}_k^{\text{out}}, \quad (23)$$

where \mathcal{M} denotes the set of attacked nodes.

Assumption 7 ensures that every non-attacked node has at least one out-neighbor where the alarm will not be triggered. This property, combined with the definition of \mathcal{V}_a in (22), is key to achieving attack isolation, as demonstrated in the subsequent proposition.

Proposition 5. *Let Assumptions 1–7 hold. Consider the observer defined by (6) for system (1), where the SMO*

Fig. 2: Interconnection topology of the six-subsystem case study. Nodes 2 and 6 are under attack.

gain satisfies the condition specified in (12) for all $i \in \mathcal{V}$. Moreover, let $e \in \sigma(e)$, where $\sigma(e)$ follows from (8), and \mathcal{M} be the set of attacked nodes. Then, $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{V}_a$, where \mathcal{V}_a follows from (22).

Proposition 5 confirms the accurate identification of all attacked nodes, ensuring that no non-attacked nodes are misclassified as attacked, and vice versa.

Remark 1. The proposed distributed scheme employs the designed SMOs to effectively isolate attacks. While the literature has extensively addressed distributed sensor anomaly isolation (both attacks and faults) without relying on Assumptions 6 and 7 (e.g., [9], [14]–[16]), existing methods often impose various restrictions, such as combinatorial complexity in isolation schemes, which can limit their practical applicability. Future work will focus on relaxing Assumptions 6 and 7 to improve the effectiveness of the developed approach.

VI. MAIN RESULT

The following theorem integrates the results from Sections III (Attack Reconstruction) and V (Attack Isolation), establishing the comprehensive conditions necessary for attack reconstruction and isolation within the proposed scheme.

Theorem 1. Let Assumptions 1–7 hold. Consider the observer in (6) for system (1), where the SMO gain satisfies (12) for all $i \in \mathcal{V}$. Moreover, let $e \in \sigma(e)$, where $\sigma(e)$ follows from (8), and \mathcal{M} be the set of attacked nodes. Then, the reconstructed attack signal, as defined in (15), satisfies

$$\|\delta^i - \hat{\delta}^i\| \leq \epsilon^i, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{M},$$

where ϵ^i is given by (18), and $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{V}_a$, where \mathcal{V}_a follows from (22).

Follows directly from Propositions 4 and 5.

Theorem 1 establishes that, given specific conditions regarding the magnitude and location of attacks within the interconnected subsystems, Problem 1 can be effectively solved. This implies the capability to isolate any attacked subsystem and accurately reconstruct the attack signal within a defined margin of error.

VII. SIMULATION

To validate the proposed distributed detection and reconstruction scheme, we conduct numerical experiments in MATLAB on a network of six interconnected subsystems. The communication graph is shown in Figure 2. Each subsystem is described by the state-space form in (5). For each node $i \in \mathcal{V}$, the local state-transition, input, and output matrices (A^i, B^i, C^i) are specified as follows:

$$A^i = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[\begin{array}{ccc} -17.5 & 0.4 & 1.9 \\ 0.3 & -18.8 & 0.8 \\ 0.3 & 1 & -18.7 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{cc} -16.9 & 0.4 \\ 0.4 & -18 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{ccc} -18.1 & 0.3 & 0.5 \\ 0.9 & -17.4 & 0.6 \\ 0.6 & 0.7 & -17.7 \end{array} \right], \\ \left[\begin{array}{ccc} -17.9 & 0.7 & \\ 0.6 & -18.3 & \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{ccc} -10.5 & 0.9 & 1.5 \\ 0.1 & -14.6 & 0.5 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{ccc} -17.8 & 0.6 & 1 \\ 0.7 & -17.3 & 0.8 \\ 0.7 & 0.7 & -18.6 \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right\}$$

$$B^i = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[\begin{array}{c} 1.2 \\ -0.5 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 0.9 \\ 1.1 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 1.1 \\ 0.5 \\ -0.5 \end{array} \right], \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} -1.2 \\ 2.3 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 0.8 \\ -0.5 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 2.1 \\ -0.5 \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right\}, C^i = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[\begin{array}{ccc} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 0 \\ 1 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{ccc} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \right], \\ \left[\begin{array}{c} 0 \\ 1 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{c} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{array} \right], \left[\begin{array}{ccc} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{array} \right] \end{array} \right\}.$$

The coupling matrices \mathcal{H}^i are randomly generated with entries in $(0, 2)$. Subsystems 2 and 6 are attacked ($\mathcal{M} = \{2, 6\}$) with out-neighbors $\mathcal{N}_6^{\text{out}} = \{1, 4\}$ and $\mathcal{N}_2^{\text{out}} = \{3\}$. Assumption 7 holds.

A replay attack is launched at $t = 3$ s, modeled as

$$\delta^i(t) = (-y^i(t) + y^i(t-1)) \mathbf{1}(t-3), \quad i \in \mathcal{M},$$

which explicitly introduces a nonzero rate-of-change $\dot{\delta}^i$. Disturbances satisfy $\|w^i\| < 0.03$. During the attack, the signals satisfy $0.22 < \|\delta^2\| < 0.23$ and $0.0981 < \|\delta^6\| < 0.1247$.

Fig. 3: Comparison between reconstructed signal norm $\|\hat{\delta}^i\|$ and threshold ϵ^i . Subsystem 5 remains below threshold since it is not in $\{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}_2^{\text{out}} \cup \mathcal{N}_6^{\text{out}}\}$.

Figure 3 illustrates the detection mechanism. Before $t = 3$, all reconstructed norms remain below thresholds, preventing false alarms. When the replay attacks occur, subsystems 2 and 6, as well as their out-neighbors, cross the thresholds. Subsystem 5, not connected to attacked nodes, stays unaffected. According to (22), the candidate set is $\mathcal{V}_a = \{2, 6\}$, which Proposition 5 confirms as the true attacked set.

Figure 4 highlights reconstruction accuracy. The top plots show that $\hat{\delta}^i$ closely follows the true attack δ^i . The bottom plots compare the reconstruction error norm $\|\delta^i - \hat{\delta}^i\|$ with the theoretical bound ϵ^i . After a short transient, the error remains strictly below its bound, despite the presence of $\dot{\delta}^i$. These results confirm that the proposed scheme achieves both reliable attack detection and accurate reconstruction under dynamic replay attack conditions.

Fig. 4: *Top Row:* Reconstructed attack $\hat{\delta}^i$ vs. actual attack δ^i for subsystems 2 and 6. *Bottom Row:* Error norm $\|\delta^i - \hat{\delta}^i\|$ compared with the theoretical bound ϵ^i .

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a distributed scheme that utilizes SMOs for the reconstruction of attack signals targeting sensors and the isolation of the attacked nodes in large scale linear CPS. This approach is particularly significant given the increasing vulnerability of CPS to cyber-attacks that manipulate sensor measurements. By effectively leveraging local observations, the proposed scheme enables suitable bounds on the reconstruction error that depend on the disturbance characteristics of the system. Moreover, it is analytically shown that the developed isolation approach accurately determines the attacked nodes. The simulation results validate the theoretical analysis, demonstrating that the proposed scheme accurately identifies the compromised subsystems and reconstructs the attack signals. This capability enables accurate measurements and countermeasures, while the distributed architecture enables scalability and mitigates the risks associated with single points of failure.

Future work will aim to relax the gain and network conditions imposed in this work, to enable the reconstruction of a larger class of attacks and to also identify the attack types.

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